

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE MADE WITH CEMENT PARTIALLY REPLACED WITH CASSAVA PEEL ASH

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ABSTRACT

This work determines the suitability of Cassava Peel Ash (CPA) as partial replacement of cement in concrete in a bid to devise more economical construction measures while preserving strength and protecting the environment. Tests to determine the chemical composition of the CPA, specific gravity and sieve analysis of the aggregates in accordance with BS 812 standards and slump test of the concrete were carried out. In the experiments, 0-50% with 5% increment of CPA was used as partial replacement of cement in concrete. The concrete was batched by weight with a ratio of 1:2:4. Compressive strength test was conducted on the samples at interval of 7 days and some of the results obtained in N/mm² were 10.50, 16.00, 16.50, 19.50 for 0 %, 9.50,15.50, 15.60, 18.00 for 5 %, 6.80, 13.40, 14.10, 15.00 for 30 %, 5.90, 12.00, 13.50, 14.20 for 40 %, 5.50, 11.70, 12.9,13.70 for 45 %, 5.30, 11.20, 12.00, 13.10 for 50 % partial replacement conducted for 7, 14, 21 and 28 days curing respectively. The graph plotted showed that compressive strength of the concrete increased with increase in length of curing, but decreased as the percentage of cassava peel ash was increased. However, the strength still remained in the allowable range of workability for concrete in line with the British standard. Also, it was found out that the entire mix was suitable since the results were within the acceptable limits as concrete strength made with varying amounts of cassava peel ash did not fall below half of the original strength of the concrete made with zero percent CPA. This alternative use of cassava peelings will in the long run reduce cost of construction, attract higher economic value to cassava peels and increase the economic return of the farmers and preserve the environment.

Keywords: concrete, cassava, aggregates, strength, pozzolana, cement

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is an important factor of strength and support in Civil Engineering construction works. It is made from a mix of cement, coarse and fine aggregates (such as granite, gravel or stone base), and sand in the medium of water (Tantawi, 1988). This mix produces a hydrated strong binding medium with good and quick setting properties. These calcareous (calcium carbonate) and argillaceous materials (clay) could be altered in quantity, depending on the nature and strength requirement of the particular construction work. Portland cement basically contains lime, iron (III) oxide, magnesium oxide, calcium sulphate and silica in given relative quantities, depending on the specific nature of the cement (Punmatharith et al., 2010).

Part of the challenges causing substandard constructions and collapse of building and structures is compromise in the mix ratio arising from the desire to save cost. This compromise is becoming more severe with the rise in cost of materials being experienced now, particularly in the developing world. There is the need therefore to prospect for cheap but competitive materials that could be used as adjunct to the most expensive component – Cement, in the concrete formulation. This could lead to a reduction in the quantity of cement used without compromising quality, and safety in concrete production. It will also boost the dire need to develop blended cement which will be readily available to provide low-cost housing for the continually increasing population.

Cellulosic materials are agro-waste which are of economic values and which also constitutes environmental nuisance particularly during little or no harvest season. These include, rice husk, cassava peel, groundnut shell, palm oil chaff, maize cob and maize stalk (Ugwuoke *et al.*, 2018). When they are heated above 700°C for about 90 minutes, they provide pozzolana which can be used as adjunct in concrete as part of replacement for Portland cement. This partial replacement of cement has the effect of reducing the total cost of the concrete cement and indirectly ridding the environment of nuisance agricultural waste materials. Cassava (*Manihot Esculenta*) peel is an attractive candidate in this regard.

Cassava is commonly grown in West Africa, where Nigeria is one of the leading World producers, therefore, its peel abounds in the environment. When the pozzolanic material contained in the Cassava peel is blended with Portland cement, it reacts with the lime to produce additional calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) which is the major cementing component (Kale, 1981). Additionally, this mixture helps to reduce the dispersion potential of clay in the construction industry (Vakili *et al.*, 2013). The compressive strength of concrete made with Cassava Peel Ash partially replacing cement in the range of 5 – 15% only experience minimal loss of strength (Raheem *et al.*, 2015). According to Familusi *et al.* (2019), 5% partial replacement of cement with Cassava Peel Ash gives the optimal compressive strength of concrete. Other materials that can serve directly for partial cement replacement in concrete are palm

kernel shell and periwinkle shells. This has the potential of lowering the cost of concrete production in construction and building works.

Pozzolana is composed of inorganic materials that are non-biodegradable and non-combustibles, which were bio-accumulated in the process of plant growth and development. They are primarily metals and oxides of metals which serve for structural up-building of plants and also facilitates plants' biochemical and physiological functions (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015). Like silicious materials, they have the potentials of contributing to strength and cementing properties as does Calcium Carbonate and lime in the production of cement (Malhotra and Mehta, 1996). Analysis of Pozzolana showed presence of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, FeO₃, CaO, MgO, Na₂O, K₂O, and SO₃ (Kolawole *et al.*, 2014). The objective of this study therefore, is to examine the sequential partial replacement of Portland cement in concrete production using pozzolana obtained from Cassava (*Manihot Esculenta*) Peel Ash (CPA) as an adjunct material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

- (a) Samples:
- (i) Dangote ordinary Portland cement (42.5 R)
 - (ii) Fine aggregates (sand) of 1.5 mesh size 4.75 mm
 - (iii) Coarse aggregate (granite) of > 4.75 mm
 - (iv) Cassava (*Manihot Esculenta*) peels
 - (v) Water
- (b) Reagents: Sodium pyrosulphate (powdered), concentrated H₂SO₄, HF acid, ammonium nitrate solution, mixed oxide solution, ammonium thiocyanate, mercurous nitrate solution, hydrochloric acid, ammonium oxalate solution, ammonium hydroxide, calcium oxalate, potassium permanganate, concentrated nitric acid, ammonium salts, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, magnesium pyrophosphate, ammonium chloride, calcium carbonate,

barium chloride solution, ammonium carbonate, perchloric acid, alcoholic potassium perchlorate, ethyl acetate, bromine water.

- (c) Apparatus: Platinum crucible, low ash filter, test tubes, porcelain crucible, beakers, dessicator, conical flask, platinum basin, funnel, 50 ml capacity density bottles, wash bottles, sensitive weighing balance, soft adsorbent, cloth, sample divider, water bath, stack of sieves of various sizes, mechanical shaker, oven, brush, mortar and pestle, slump cone, tapping rod.
- (d) Equipment: Mixer, shovel, trowel, iron moulds, vibrating table, set of spanners fresh water pool compression machine.

METHODS

Sample Collection

- (i) Dangote ordinary Portland cement (42.5 R) was purchased from an open shop in Benin city.
- (ii) Fine aggregates (sand) was purchased from the open market in Benin City.
- (iii) Coarse aggregate (granite) was purchased from an open market in Benin City.
- (iv) Cassava peels were obtained from a cassava processing mill in Benin City.
- (v) Water was sourced from the laboratory supply.

Samples preparation

- (i) Cassava peel: The cassava peel was dried for one week, then burnt in an enclosed setting and ashed completely and pulverized until it became fine and powdery. It was then sieved to remove coarse particles.
- (ii) Aggregates: The granite and sand were dried in open air in the laboratory for five days. A 4.75 mm sieve was used to obtain finer particles of sand and used also to eliminate finer particles from the granite.

Determination of the Chemical Composition of Cassava peel Ash (CPA)

(i) Determination of Silica (SiO_2)

To the crucible containing the oxides, we added about 5 to 7 g of powdered sodium or potassium pyrosulphate and covered the crucible with its lid. Heat was applied sufficiently to keep the pyrosulphate melted. After about 15 mins, the temperature was raised slowly to avoid excessive frothing, to below dull-red and the heat was maintained at the temperature until the melt appeared to be clear. It was cooled and transferred to a glass beaker and 20 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was cautiously added and then diluted to 150 ml with water. The residue was washed five times with water and ignited in a platinum crucible. The melted substance was dissolved in the solution of the pyrosulphate melt and the solution evaporated until fumes of sulphuric acid were evolved then it was allowed to cool. The fumed liquid was cautiously diluted to about 200 ml with water and heated and filtered through a rapid, low-ash filter paper. The precipitate was washed seven times with hot water. The filtrate was evaporated and the precipitate ignited at about 1200°C in a platinum crucible. Then one drop of concentrated sulphuric acid and four drops of hydrofluoric acid were added and the silica was volatilized.

(ii) Determination of Aluminum Oxide (Al_2O_3)

100 ml out of 250 ml portion of the mixed oxide solution was taken and the mixed oxides were precipitated. Then the precipitates were washed with hot ammonium nitrate solution until it was free from sulphate. The precipitate together with the filter paper were removed and placed in a platinum crucible and heated to mass. The filter paper was charred slowly in order to avoid bursting into flame and ignited at 1100°C for about two hours. Then it was cooled and weighed and the ignition repeated to constant mass.

(iii) Determination of Iron Oxide (FeO_3)

10 ml of the solution was taken and sufficient concentrated sulphuric acid was added. Also, 5 ml of ammonium thiocyanate solution was added and the solution shaken thoroughly. We titrated with standard mercurous nitrate solution, shaking throughout. When the red colour changed to brown or orange, the solution was warmed to 60° c and the titration was completed by adding drops of the reagent slowly until the colour just disappeared. Calculations were made based on the fact that 1ml of decinormal mercurous nitrate solution is equivalent to 0.007984g of iron oxide (FeO₃).

(iv) Determination of Calcium Oxide (CaO)

To the filtrate from the separation of iron group, 1ml of dilute hydrochloric acid was added and evaporated down to 200 ml and 20 ml of boiling ammonium oxalate solution was added to the boiling liquid. Dilute ammonium hydroxide solution was added drop by drop until the solution became just alkaline. It was boiled for 5 minutes and the precipitate of calcium oxalate was allowed to stand for an hour at 90° c. The precipitate was filtered through a rapid low-ash filter paper and washed with hot water until free from chloride and oxalate. The precipitate was dissolved in 20 ml of dilute sulphuric acid and 75 ml of hot water was added and the solution was warmed to temperature of 70° c and titrated with a decinormal solution of potassium permanganate. Calculations were made based on the fact that 1ml of decinormal potassium permanganate is equivalent to 0.002804g of calcium oxide (CaO).

(v) Determination of Magnesium Oxide (MgO)

After evaporating the filtrate from the calcium separation, with a small volume until crystals separated, it was cooled and 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid was added and slowly heated to hasten the decomposition of the ammonium salts. The operation was repeated with further 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid. 20 ml of hot water was added to the dried mass followed by 2 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered for any

suspended impurities found and diluted to 150 ml with water. 20 ml of diammonium hydrogen phosphate solution was added followed by 20 ml of concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution and it was kept overnight in a cold place. Then filtered through a rapid, low-ash filter paper and the precipitate washed with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution until the filtrate was free from chloride and phosphate. Then the precipitate was transferred with the filter paper into the porcelain crucible and charred at a low heat so that the filter paper does not burst into flames. The temperature was raised to burn off carbon, and the precipitate ignited at 1100°C for one hour taking care to note that no black mass resulted, then it was cooled and weighed. Calculations were made based on the fact that 1g of magnesium pyrophosphate corresponds to 0.3621g of magnesium oxide (MgO).

(vi) Determination of Alkalis (Na_2O , K_2O)

It was extremely important to take note that specifically prepared reagents as free as possible from alkali metals were used. Mix of 0.8g of bulk ash accurately weighed 0.8g of ammonium chloride and 6g of precipitated calcium carbonate by grinding together in an agate mortar. The mixture was transferred to a platinum crucible fitted with a lid, a little calcium carbonate having been placed previously at the bottom of the crucible. The crucible was placed in a suitable shield of asbestos-cement board so arranged that only the lower half of the crucible is directly heated. It was heated gently until ammonia ceased to evolved, then the temperature was raised to about 700°C (dull red heat) maintaining at this temperature for 75 mins. The cooled sintered mass was then slaked with about 5 ml of water and the contents of the crucible transferred to a beaker and digested with 50 ml of hot water. It was left to settle and then the supernatant liquid was decanted through a fine filter paper. The digestion and decantation was repeated twice, finally transferring the residue to the filter paper. It was washed with hot water and the residue discarded. Any sulphate that was present in the combined filtrates was

precipitated by the addition, in the normal manner, of barium chloride solution, slightly acidified with hydrochloric acid and filtered through a fine filter paper and discard the residue. The filtrate was treated successively with slight excesses of both concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution and ammonium carbonate solution. It was filtered through a fine filter paper, and the precipitate was redissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitation process repeated and filtration. Residue was discarded again and the combined filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a platinum basin and all the ammonium salts removed by careful baking in a muffle furnace at 450°C . Then, the sides of the basin were rinsed down with 25 ml of hot water. Dilute barium chloride solution was added in drops until one drop causes no further precipitation. Then 1 ml of dilute ammonium oxalate solution was added followed by 2 ml of ammonium carbonate solution and one drop of concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution. The mixture was allowed to stand for at least 4 hours, preferably overnight. Then, it was filtered through a small, fine, filter paper into a platinum basin and washing the precipitate three times with water and then the precipitate was discarded. After that, the precipitate was evaporated to dryness and the ammonium salts were removed and the baked residue extracted with 5 to 10 ml of hot water and filtered through a small, fine, filter paper into a weighted platinum basin, washing the paper mix six times with hot water. Then the residue discarded and 10 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid added to the filtrate and evaporated to dryness. It was then heated in a muffle furnace at 450°C . Then it was cooled in a desiccator and reweighed. The increase in the mass was regarded as the mass of mixed alkali chlorides present. The mixed chlorides are then dissolved in about 5 ml of water and transferred to a small evaporating basin of good quality glass and 2 ml of perchloric acid added and left gently to evaporate to dryness on a hot plate which is not above 350°C . It is then cooled and 5 ml of water added and left to evaporate to dryness as before. A 50 ml conical flask

and a filter stick is dried and weighed together, then the filter stick is removed temporarily to a desiccator or stoppered tube. We now transfer the dried residue from the evaporating basin to the conical flask by successive rinsings with 2ml of hot water. Then we evaporate to dryness in the flask, finishing in an oven for about one hour at about 110°C . Then cooled in a desiccators and 5 ml of pure ethyl acetate or absolute alcohol saturated potassium perchlorate, the flask is corked and the liquids swirled around gently for about 5 mins. Then the cork is removed and filter stick connected to a suction pump and inserted into the solution. Then we insert a strap between the filter stick and the pump to catch the filtrate. Much of the solution was taken through the filter stick and the inside of the flask and the outside of the filter stick washed down with four separate portions of 5 ml of ethyl acetate, while drawing each separation portions through the filter stick. The lower portion of the flask was immersed while suction was still applied in hot water and the vapour of ethyl acetate was drawn out. Then the filter stick was detached again and the flask and stick dried at 110°C to constant mass. The increase in mass was potassium perchlorate and for extreme accuracy and to correct for the amount dissolved by ethyl acetate, 0.0003g was added to the mass of potassium perchlorate found, and the amount of alkalis were calculated based on the following:

- (a) 1g of potassium perchlorate is equivalent to 0.5381g of potassium chloride (KCl).
- (b) 1g of potassium chloride is equivalent to 0.6314g of potassium oxide (K_2O).
- (c) 1g of sodium chloride is equivalent to 0.530g of sodium oxide (Na_2O).

(vii) Determination of Sulphuric Oxide (SO_3)

The determination of sulphuric oxide was carried out on a standard ash with 5 ml of bromine water and 100 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid and boiled for one hour. It was then filtered through a fine filter paper and the insoluble residue washed with hot water and the residue reserved. The filtrate is then neutralized with concentrated ammonium

hydroxide solution and 2 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Volume of about 250 ml was made up and the solution boiled and while boiling, treated with 15 ml of concentrated barium chloride solution, added in drops to permit uninterrupted boiling. Boiling was continued for a further 15 minutes and allowed to stand for a minimum period of 4 hours in a sulphur free atmosphere and protected from dust. It was then filtered by gravity through an ashless fine-textured double acid-washed filter paper in a fluted, long stemmed 60° funnel, and the filtrate circle being carefully folded to fit the funnel so that the stem remains full of liquid.

Experimentation on concrete and its constituents

(i) Determination of specific gravity for the prepared samples

The specific gravity tests were carried out for each concrete component using standard methods for the fine aggregates, coarse aggregates and cassava peel ash (CPA). Average values were recorded for two samples of the prepared concrete component.

(ii) Determination of Particle size distribution

Sieve analysis or gradation tests were carried out using standard sieves according to standard methods for the fine and coarse aggregates.

(iii) Mixing, Casting, Compaction and Demolding

A mix ratio of 1:2:4 was used for all mixes and the aggregates were batched by weight and mixing of concrete was carried out in a planetary mixer of 100 l capacity and mixing was kept at a minimum of 3 mins with proper stirring with a shovel. The process of mixing and obtaining the required concrete were carried out as follows:

- (i) The aggregates were poured in one after the other in no particular order including the CPA.
- (ii) A portion of the designed amount of water for the mix ratio was gently added.

- (iv) Then the mixer was started and with the use of a shovel, proper stirring of the concrete was ensured whilst the mixer was operating and the remaining portion of the water added to ensure uniform mixture and workability.
- (v) After about 3 mins, the mixer was stopped and the oiled moulds were filled with the concrete and then taken to the vibrator and vibrated until proper compaction is achieved in order for the concrete mix to attain maximum strength.
- (v) Specimens were then prepared and left for 24 hours to set.
- (vi) After 24 hours, the specimens were demoulded with the use of the spanners and placed in water for curing to take place for 7 days, 14 days, 21 days and 28 days for each mix.

(vi) Curing

Curing of the concrete cubes was done in the laboratory in the curing room as follows:

- (i) After the cubes were fully set and demoulded, they were taken to the curing pool and immersed in the water fully.

(v) Compressive strength test

- (i) After the concrete cubes have been cured to the designated number of days, they were brought out and dried to eliminate all the moisture content and then weighed; they were placed in the machine and clamped, then the compression machine was started and the value at which the cube cracked was recorded. This process was carried out on all the cubes cast. The compressive strength of the concrete cubes was calculated by dividing the aggregate crushing values (in kilonewtons) of the cubes by their area. The cubes cast were of dimensions 100mm x 100mm (0.1m x 0.1m).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following results were obtained from the experiments carried out in the laboratory.

Table 3.1: Results of the Chemical composition of Cassava Peel Ash (CPA)

Component	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	FeO ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃
Percentage composition	36.79	3.10	2.50	64.50	1.70	1.70	0.85	2.50

Table 3.2: Results for the specific gravity test for the prepared samples

Prepared sample	Specific gravity		
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Average value
Fine aggregates	2.61	2.59	2.63
Coarse aggregates (granite)	2.64	2.68	2.66
Cassava peel ash	1.89	2.01	1.95

Table 3.3: Sieve Analysis Results for Coarse Aggregates (BS 812 (1985) Part 103)

BS Sieve Size (mm)	Mass of retained material (g)	Percentage of Material retained
19.0	0	0
13.2	44.0	4.4
9.5	122	16.7
6.7	267	43.4
5.0	522	95.6
4.5	44.0	100

Table 3.4: Sieve Analysis Results for Fine Aggregates (BS 812 (1996))

BS Sieve Size (mm)	Mass of retained material (g)	Percentage of material retained
4.75	1.0	0.1
2.36	48	4.9
1.18	139	18.7
0.6	357	54.4
0.3	323	86.7
0.15	123	99.0

Table 3.5: Results of the mix proportions of concrete components and workability

Cement replacement (%)	Cement (kg)	Water (kg)	Fine aggregates (kg)	Coarse aggregates (kg)	CPA (kg)	Slump (workability) with 0.5 (w/C)
0	4.0	2.0	9.0	19.0	0	30
5	3.8	2.0	9.0	19.0	0.2	26
10	3.6	2.0	9.0	19.0	0.4	25
15	3.4	2.0	9.0	19.0	0.6	22
20	3.2	2.0	9.0	19.0	0.8	19
25	3.0	2.0	9.0	19.0	1.0	18
30	2.8	2.0	9.0	19.0	1.2	18
35	2.6	2.0	9.0	19.0	1.4	17
40	2.4	2.0	9.0	19.0	1.6	14
45	2.2	2.0	9.0	19.0	1.8	12
50	2.0	2.0	9.0	19.0	2.0	11

Table 3.6: Results of compressive strength of unreplaced cement concrete and concrete made with cement partially replaced with cassava peel ash at different length of curing days

% CPA content in concrete	Range of mass (kg)	Average mass (kg)	Range of density (kg/m ³) (10 ³)	Average density (kg/m ³) (10 ³)	Compressive strength of concrete (N/mm ²)			
					Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
0	2.42 - 2.58	2.48	2.42 – 2.58	2.48	10.5	16.0	16.5	19.5
5	2.40 – 2.55	2.48	2.40 – 2.55.	2.48	9.5	15.5	15.6	18.0
10	2.36 – 2.54	2.43	2.36 – 2.54	2.43	8.8	15.2	15.3	17.0
15	2.38 – 2.54	2.45	2.38 – 2.54	2.45	8.0	14.5	15.0	16.5
20	2.40 – 2.60	2.51	2.40 – 2.60	2.51	7.5	14.2	14.8	15.5
25	2.43 – 2.62	2.49	2.43 – 2.62	2.49	7.1	13.9	14.6	15.3
30	2.40 – 2.51	2.46	2.40 – 2.51	2.46	6.8	13.4	14.1	15.0
35	2.33 – 2.52	2.46	2.33 – 2.52	2.46	6.3	13.1	13.8	14.7
40	2.31 – 2.58	2.41	2.31 – 2.58	2.41	5.9	12.0	13.5	14.2
45	2.30 – 2.50	2.39	2.30 – 2.50	2.39	5.5	11.7	12.9	13.7
50	2.21 – 2.46	2.35	2.21 – 2.46	2.35	5.3	11.2	12.0	13.1

DISCUSSION

Concrete cubes made from different partial replacement of cement with cassava peel ash (CPA) were cured in fresh water for different number of days and their masses, densities, volume, area, aggregate crushing value and compressive strength were outlined in the tables for each cement partial replacement percentage. This was done after carrying out a comprehensive test on the chemical composition of the CPA, to ascertain the presence of pozzolana and their proportions. The presence of chemical constituents such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and CaO in the Pozzolana which is also present in Cement implies the CPA offers some cementing properties to the concrete. The compressive strength test was carried out because the compressive strength of concrete determines the ability of structures to withstand the load imposed on them. In order to predict the load bearing capacity of a structure therefore, the compressive strength of the concrete of the prescribed mix can be used. This characteristic is usually determined by the cement

component. The aggregate and the sand quality also play major roles in determining the compressive strength of a concrete. The specific gravity of the fine aggregate was 2.63 which is between 2.60 and 2.80 which indicates that it is an inorganic sandy soil. The specific gravity of the coarse aggregate was 2.66 which signify that it is granite. Details of results of sieve analysis for both the fine and coarse aggregates were given in accordance with BS 812 (1996) and BS 812 (1985) part 103 respectively. From the values of slump obtained in the experiment as stipulated in the table 4, the slump only reduced from 30 mm to 11 mm from the control mix 0% to 50% replacement of cement with CPA respectively. The standard values of slump required for the different working conditions shows that the concrete remains stable in the range of very low to low workability (Oladipo *et al.*, 2013). This means they can be applied on road vibrated by mechanical power operated machine and hand operated machine in accordance with the provision of the - BS 4550 method of testing cement British Standard Institute London shown (Nervile and Brooks, 1987). In other words, the concrete embedded with CPA up to 50 percent constituent is still stable and could be acceptable in most concrete work in building industry. Further research showed that the strength of cement-CPA concrete tends to merge up with those of normal concrete, especially at later age (56 days and above), when not more than 15% CPA is used and from the values of the compressive strength gotten, concrete made with unreplaced cement (control) at 28 days strength was not up to two times the value of the strength of concrete made with CPA replacing cement by 50% at 28 days which makes the strength acceptable (Oladipo *et al.*, 2013). Figure 3.1 shows the variation of the compressive strength against percentage replacement of cement with CPA at different curing days.

Figure 3.1: Graph of compressive strength against percentage cement replacement with CPA

This signifies that there is an increase in strength of the concrete with increase in length of curing for all the mixes. However, the plot also attests to the fact that the compressive strength of the concrete decreases with increase in the CPA content. Therefore, CPA content ranging from 5% to 10% offer more concrete strength and hence are more suitable for construction.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Finding alternative economic use for waste is sustainable, as the incentive to pay adequate attention to the environment will be high. Cassava peels that currently constitutes waste in Nigeria can best be managed through alternative use. This study has found a secondary recycling technique for cassava peel which customarily had no re-use option. The produced concrete adds to the group of prestressed concrete. This research is geared towards providing information on one of the ways of using cassava

peels in the most economical way which will have significant impact in the construction industry. From the experiments carried out, it was observed that the slump test revealed that concrete with cassava peels constituent has low workability. It was also observed that concrete cured in fresh water increases in strength with age of curing and concrete made with cement partially replaced with cassava peel ash (CPA) cured in fresh water increases in strength with age of curing and reduces in strength with increase in cassava peel ash content. Despite the reduction in concrete strength with increase in CPA content, the strength recorded were stable and within acceptable limits in line with British standards. This is ideal for concrete work in building construction. Through the implementation of the outcome of this research, the industrial demand for cassava peels may in no distant time outweigh supply. This mechanism will put a higher premium on cassava peels. The economic return of cassava production will creep from its poor status to higher level. The environment will be better maintained, the cost of construction will be reduced, and there will be reduction in greenhouse effect of cement production through evolution of CO₂ and the farmers will reap more economic return on their investment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the experiment carried out and the results gotten, it is recommended that concrete should be made with cement partially replaced with cassava peel ash (CPA). This is important for the purpose of reducing cost of construction and reducing or eliminating the hazards caused by cassava peel waste in the environment. This will also reduce the greenhouse effect that is caused by CO₂ emission in cement production and save energy.

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